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PERSONALIZATION OF SERVICES AND NEW TOOLS THAT AFFECT STANDARDS OF QUALITY IN THE SECTOR OF BEAUTY AND COMMERCIAL MEDICINE

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Abstract

This article discusses the basic principles of a quality management system, quality standards in service organizations, the purpose of which is to continuously improve the company's activities and increase their competitiveness. The article focuses on the problem of attracting new customers in the salons. One of the basic principles of the management system is customer orientation, customer capital. The paramount importance is the provision of high-quality cosmetic services with high-quality products using the algorithm "Personalization of the offer for new clients based on the digital technology".

Keywords: Cosmetic care, evaluation, purchase, entrepreneurs, paramount, personalization, commercial medicine, provision, innovative approach.

The range of services offered at small enterprises in the beauty industry is constantly expanding, innovative materials and processes are being introduced. As you know, small businesses in the beauty industry are able to quickly respond to changes in consumer demand, provide a quick return on costs and have great opportunities to implement an individual approach to customers. However, the problem of attracting new customers to the salons, as well as forming a permanent circle of customers, is still acute, which allows us to achieve sustainable profit growth.

"Customer orientation" is one of the main principles of the quality management system. The companies' customer capital consists of current and past customers who have interacted with the company and its products, as well as future subscribers who may be interested in offering it later. In this context, the ability to communicate and influence consumers is critical to the company's value creation and competitiveness processes, as well as to ensure its proper and sustainable functioning in the future. Consumer behavior can be defined as the process of making decisions that affect individuals and groups during the evaluation, purchase, use, and further disposal of goods and services (Brady & Cronin, 2001). By adapting their behavior to different customer groups, entrepreneurs can better meet the expectations of individual consumers and thus ensure their satisfaction and interest.

For the high-quality provision of cosmetic care, the quality of the doctor's work, the use of highly effective cosmetics and technical devices that can have a

positive effect on the disturbed physiological and biochemical processes in the skin due to various, including environmental factors are of paramount importance. The quality of the work of the doctor himself is determined by his knowledge and manual skills acquired in the process of implementing the medical service, analyzing its effect in the near and long-term observation periods. This is where the need for discussion arises: where it is appropriate to talk about medical technologies, and where it is appropriate to talk about standards (Behn, 2003).

The problem that exists in the service organizations (in the beauty industry) within the framework of the quality management system is the lack of proper orientation to the consumer (the consumer experience of customers, their feedback on previous visits to other beauty salons, insufficient personalization of the provided offer is not taken into account) (Scott & Odum, 2015). This problem can be solved by using the algorithm "Personalization of the offer for new customers", based on the use of a digital footprint and digital technologies.

The database available at enterprises contains a minimum set of information, including the last name, first name, patronymic, address, phone number and the number of requests for the service (not always). This does not allow you to track the "history" of the customer. The sites themselves are boring and monotonous, difficult to understand. Working with regular customers is reduced to providing discounts. There is no customer feedback. This is despite the fact that feedback from citizens is considered as "a key element of

program and campaign evaluation" and is often used to measure satisfaction with programs and services (Farn-dale & Murrer, 2015). Given the above, it can be concluded that most companies in the fashion and beauty industry are not focused on establishing permanent strong relationships with customers, do not care about retaining customers and studying their needs.

Personalization of services becomes a determining factor in attracting new customers. It is impossible to ensure this process without creating an information client base. The data collected in the customer base allows you to evaluate the typology of service consumers. A permanent customer base allows you to differentiate customers, facilitates the process of implementing a customer-oriented policy at the enterprise and evaluating customer loyalty. High competition among the beauty industry enterprises forces us to look for new innovative approaches to working with customers (Behn, 2003).

It is possible to achieve the goal of meeting the needs of the consumer, provided that the manager is constantly interested in the needs and desires of the customers. The concept of "your own" buyer appears. Today's consumers are highly informed and discerning people. The desire to retain regular customers and get new ones, especially young people, requires a differentiated approach to each customer.

Experts identify several basic quality characteristics:

1. Professional competence;
2. Availability;
3. Performance;
4. Interpersonal relationships;
5. Effectiveness;
6. Security;
7. Convenience.

Among the quality indicators that have a double meaning, including the characteristics of the quality itself and the factor of influence on quality, the nature of the relationship between the patient and the professional is fundamental (Brady & Cronin, 2001). The concept of technology safety is predetermined, although it is impossible to talk about absolute safety, since the doctor always deals with a biological object, the behavior of which is sometimes difficult to predict due to changing conditions, the presence of allergies, concomitant diseases. The concept of technology safety is predetermined, although it is impossible to talk about absolute safety, since the doctor always deals with a biological object, the behavior of which is sometimes difficult to predict due to changing conditions, the presence of allergies, concomitant diseases (Anitha, 2014).

The standards represent the totality of all the technological links that determine the treatment program for patients with specific diseases. They include diagnostic, therapeutic and rehabilitation measures from the moment of initial treatment to the completion of the rehabilitation process. Here, economic calculations, a description of the structure and mechanism of implementation are of predominant importance, so the standards are more necessary for insurance companies, the assessment of the financial component of health care.

That is why there is no consensus on the feasibility of developing standards (Slatten, 2010).

As for such standards as educational, regulations that include technology, instructions and recommendations of leading specialists and institutions, as well as service standards, they certainly have great prospects in aesthetic medicine. Recently, they have received special attention.

Quality management at the enterprise involves solving a variety of tasks that require large expenditures of human resources. This includes the collection, analysis and systematization of a significant amount of data on the company's products, processes, services, systems; continuous monitoring of processes, their management; making important strategic decisions based on large databases, etc. Digitalization helps to translate a number of manual operations into digital format, which will help to optimize the company's time and human resources, eliminate the human factor. However, such digitalization does not imply a complete rejection of the activities of people, it only reduces the "routine processes", leaving more opportunities for the development of the creative and innovative potential of the company's employees. Therefore, the use of digital technologies will help to optimize the company's work and quickly achieve its goals (Anitha, 2014).

Quality standards in service organizations are created for the purpose of regular improvement of the company's activities and increasing the competitiveness of the company. The quality standards include the creation of a quality management system and bringing it to perfection in the process of use (Slatten, 2010). Quality standards in service companies are based on comprehensive quality management of the services provided, improvement of the technologies used and regular control over the improvement of work, orientation to consumers by analyzing their current and future needs. The development of a management system allows you to solve a large number of tasks of the company, provides a positive profit dynamics.

Service industries in Kazakhstan are also developing in the context of local economy and the industry of beauty and commercial medicine is part of this development. Quality management in this sector is strongly rely on service that a firm provides. It is necessary to introduce innovation tools that strongly increase service that specialists provide to clients of a firm. Technological advantages can strongly increase existing quality standards in beauty industry and should be implemented by companies that want to achieve high competitive advantage on the market. Further works can be dedicated to study of effectiveness of any tool or standard in the beauty and commercial medicine sector.

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